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Seismo Magnetic Moment Fractal Dimension for Characterizing Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation, Saudi Arabia

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ABSTRACT

The quality and assessment of a reservoir can be documented in details by the application of seismo magnetic moment. This research aims to calculate fractal dimension from the relationship among seismo magnetic moment, maximum seismo magnetic moment and wetting phase saturation and to approve it by the fractal dimension derived from the relationship among capillary pressure and wetting phase saturation. Two equations for calculating the fractal dimensions have been employed. The first one describes the functional relationship between wetting phase saturation, seismo magnetic moment, maximum seismo magnetic moment and fractal dimension. The second equation implies to the wetting phase saturation as a function of capillary pressure and the fractal dimension. Two procedures for obtaining the fractal dimension have been utilized. The first procedure was done by plotting the logarithm of the ratio between seismo magnetic moment and maximum seismo magnetic moment versus logarithm wetting phase saturation. The slope of the first procedure = $3 - D_f$ (fractal dimension). The second procedure for obtaining the fractal dimension was determined by plotting the logarithm of capillary pressure versus the logarithm of wetting phase saturation. The slope of the second procedure = $D_f - 3$. On the basis of the obtained results of the fabricated stratigraphic column and the attained values of the fractal dimension, the sandstones of the Shajara reservoirs of the Shajara Formation were divided here into three units.

Keywords: Shajara Reservoirs, Shajara Formation, Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension, Capillary pressure fractal dimension

1. INTRODUCTION

Seismo electric effects related to electro kinetic potential, dielectric permittivity, pressure gradient, fluid viscosity, and electric conductivity was first reported by Frenkel [1]. Capillary pressure follows the scaling law at low wetting phase saturation was reported by Li and Williams [2]. Seismo electric phenomenon by considering electro kinetic coupling coefficient as a function of effective charge density, permeability, fluid viscosity and electric conductivity was reported by Revil and Jardani [3]. The magnitude of seismo electric current depends on porosity, pore size, zeta potential of the pore surfaces, and elastic properties of the matrix was investigated by Dukhin et al [4]. The tangent of the ratio of converted electric field to pressure is approximately in inverse proportion to permeability was studied by Guan et al [5]. Permeability inversion from seismo electric log at low frequency was studied by Hu et al [6]. They reported that, the tangent of the ratio among electric excitation intensity and pressure field is a function of porosity, fluid viscosity, frequency, tortuosity and fluid density and Darcy permeability. A decrease of seismo electric frequencies with increasing water content was reported by Borde et al [7]. An increase of seismo electric transfer function with increasing water saturation was studied by Jardani and Revil [8]. An increase of dynamic seismo electric transfer function with decreasing fluid conductivity was described by Holzhauer et al [9]. The amplitude of seismo electric signal increases with increasing permeability which means that the seismo electric effects are directly related to the permeability and can be used to study the permeability of the reservoir was illustrated by Ping et al [10]. Seismo electric coupling is frequency dependent and decreases exponentially when frequency increases was demonstrated by Djuraev et al [11]. An increase of permeability with increasing pressure head and bubble pressure fractal dimension was reported by Alkhidir [12, 13]. An increase of geometric relaxation time of induced polarization fractal dimension with permeability increasing and grain size was described by Alkhidir [14].

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Sandstone samples were collected from the surface type section of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation, latitude 26° 52' 17.4", longitude 43° 36' 18". (Figure 1). Porosity was measured on collected samples using mercury intrusion Porosimetry and permeability was derived from capillary pressure data. The purpose of this paper is to obtain seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and to confirm it by capillary pressure fractal dimension. The fractal dimension of the first procedure is determined from the positive slope of the plot of logarithm of the ratio of seismo magnetic moment to maximum seismo magnetic moment $\log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max})$ versus \log wetting phase saturation ($\log Sw$). Whereas the fractal dimension of the second procedure is determined from the negative slope of the plot of logarithm of \log capillary pressure ($\log Pc$) versus logarithm of wetting phase saturation ($\log Sw$). The Seismo magnetic moment can be scaled as

$$Sw = \left[\frac{SMM^{1/4}}{SMM^{1/4}_{max}} \right]^{[3-Df]} \quad (1)$$

where S_w the water saturation, SMM the seismo magnetic moment in ampere * square meter, SMM_{max} the maximum seismo magnetic moment in ampere * square meter, and D_f the fractal dimension.

Equation 1 can be proofed from

$$H = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV}{\alpha^\infty * \eta} \right] \quad (2)$$

where H the seismo magnetic field in ampere / meter, ϕ the porosity, ϵ the fluid permittivity in Faraday / meter, k_f the fluid dielectric constant, the fluid density ρ_f in kilogram / cubic meter, $SSWV$ the seismic shear wave velocity in meter / second, $SRGV$ the seismo radial grain velocity in meter / second, α^∞ the tortuosity, η the fluid viscosity in pascal * second

The seismo magnetic field H can be scaled as

$$H = \left[\frac{i}{d} \right] \quad (3)$$

where H the seismo magnetic field in ampere /meter, i the electric current in ampere, d the distance in meter.

Insert equation 3 into equation 2

$$\left[\frac{i}{d} \right] = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV}{\alpha^\infty * \eta} \right] \quad (4)$$

The electric current can be scaled as

$$i = \left[\frac{SMM}{A} \right] \quad (5)$$

where i the electric current in ampere, SMM the seismo magnetic moment in ampere * square meter, A the area in meter

Insert equation 5 into equation 4

$$\left[\frac{SMM}{A} \right] = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV}{\alpha^\infty * \eta} \right] \quad (6)$$

The area can be scaled as

$$A = \left[\frac{Q * \eta * L}{k * \Delta p} \right] \quad (7)$$

where A the area in square meter, Q the flow rate in cubic meter / second , η the fluid viscosity in pascal * second, L the capillary length in meter, k the permeability in square meter, Δp the differential pressure in pascal.

Insert equation 7 into equation 6

$$\left[\frac{SMM * k * \Delta p}{Q * \eta * L} \right] = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV}{\alpha_{\infty} * \eta} \right] \quad (8)$$

Equation 8 after rearrange will become

$$\left[\frac{SMM * k * \Delta p}{\eta * L} \right] = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV * Q}{\alpha_{\infty} * \eta} \right] \quad (9)$$

The flow rate can be scaled as

$$Q = \left[\frac{3.14 * r^4 * \Delta p}{8 * \eta * L} \right] \quad (10)$$

where Q the flow rate in cubic meter / second, r the pore radius in meter, Δp the differential pressure in pascal, η the fluid viscosity in pascal * second, and L the capillary length in meter. Insert equation 10 into equation 9

$$\left[\frac{SMM * k * \Delta p}{\eta * L} \right] = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV * 3.14 * r^4 * \Delta p}{\alpha_{\infty} * \eta * 8 * \eta * L} \right] \quad (11)$$

The maximum pore radius can be scaled a

$$\left[\frac{SMM_{max} * k * \Delta p}{\eta * L} \right] = \left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV * 3.14 * r_{max}^4 * \Delta p}{\alpha_{\infty} * \eta * 8 * \eta * L} \right] \quad (12)$$

Divide equation 11 by equation 12

$$\left[\frac{\left[\frac{SMM * k * \Delta p}{\eta * L} \right]}{\left[\frac{SMM_{max} * k * \Delta p}{\eta * L} \right]} \right] = \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV * 3.14 * r^4 * \Delta p}{\alpha_{\infty} * \eta * 8 * \eta * L} \right]}{\left[\frac{\phi * \epsilon * k_f * \zeta * \rho_f * SSWV * SRGV * 3.14 * r_{max}^4 * \Delta p}{\alpha_{\infty} * \eta * 8 * \eta * L} \right]} \right] \quad (13)$$

Equation 13 after simplification will become

$$\left[\frac{SSM}{SMM_{max}} \right] = \left[\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} \right] \quad (14)$$

Take the fourth root of equation 14

$$\sqrt[4]{\left[\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} \right]} = \sqrt[4]{\left[\frac{SSM}{SMM_{max}} \right]} \quad (15)$$

Equation 15 after simplification will become

$$\left[\frac{r}{r_{\max}} \right] = \left[\frac{SSM^{\frac{1}{4}}}{SSM_{\max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right] \quad (16)$$

Take the logarithm of equation 16

$$\log \left[\frac{r}{r_{\max}} \right] = \log \left[\frac{SSM^{\frac{1}{4}}}{SSM_{\max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right] \quad (17)$$

$$\text{But; } \log \left[\frac{r}{r_{\max}} \right] = \left[\frac{\log Sw}{3 - Df} \right] \quad (18)$$

Insert equation 18 into equation 17

$$\left[\frac{\log Sw}{3 - Df} \right] = \log \left[\frac{SSM^{\frac{1}{4}}}{SSM_{\max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right] \quad (19)$$

Equation 19 after log removal will become

$$Sw = \left[\frac{SSM^{\frac{1}{4}}}{SSM_{\max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right]^{[3-Df]} \quad (20)$$

Equation 20 the proof of equation 1 which relates the water saturation, seismo magnetic moment, maximum seismo magnetic moment, and the fractal dimension. The capillary pressure can be scaled as

$$\text{LogSw} = [Df - 3] * \log pc + \text{constant} \quad (21)$$

where Sw the water saturation, Pc the capillary pressure and Df the fractal dimension.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on field observation the Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation were divided here into three units as described in Figure 1. These units from bottom to top are: Lower Shajara Reservoir, Middle Shajara reservoir, and Upper Shajara Reservoir. Their attained results of the seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and capillary pressure

fractal dimension are shown in Table 1. Based on the achieved results it was found that the seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension is equal to the capillary pressure fractal dimension. The maximum value of the fractal dimension was found to be 2.7872 allocated to sample SJ13 from the Upper Shajara Reservoir as verified in Table 1. Whereas the minimum value of the fractal dimension 2.4379 was reported from sample SJ3 from the Lower Shajara reservoir as shown in Table 1. The Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension were detected to increase with increasing permeability as proofed in Table1 owing to the possibility of having interconnected channels.

Table 1. Petrophysical model showing the three Shajara Reservoir Units with their corresponding values of seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension

Formation	Reservoir	Sample	Porosity %	k (md)	Positive slope of the first procedure Slope = 3-Df	Negative slope of the second procedure Slope = Df-3	Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension	Capillary pressure fractal dimension
Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation	Upper Shajara Reservoir	SJ13	25	973	0.2128	-0.2128	2.7872	2.7872
		SJ12	28	1440	0.2141	-0.2141	2.7859	2.7859
		SJ11	36	1197	0.2414	-0.2414	2.7586	2.7586
	Middle Shajara Reservoir	SJ9	31	1394	0.2214	-0.2214	2.7786	2.7786
		SJ8	32	1344	0.2248	-0.2248	2.7752	2.7752
		SJ7	35	1472	0.2317	-0.2317	2.7683	2.7683
	Lower Shajara Reservoir	SJ4	30	176	0.3157	-0.3157	2.6843	2.6843
		SJ3	34	56	0.5621	-0.5621	2.4379	2.4379
		SJ2	35	1955	0.2252	-0.2252	2.7748	2.7748
		SJ1	29	1680	0.2141	-0.2141	2.7859	2.7859

The Lower Shajara reservoir was symbolized by six sandstone samples (Figure 1), four of which label as SJ1, SJ2, SJ3 and SJ4 were carefully chosen for capillary pressure measurement as proven in Table 1. Their positive slopes of the first procedure log of the Seismo magnetic moment to maximum Seismo magnetic moment versus log wetting phase saturation (Sw) and negative slopes of the second procedure log capillary pressure (Pc) versus log wetting phase saturation (Sw) are clarified in Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5 and Table 1. Their Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension values are revealed in Table 1.

AGE	Fm.	Mbr.	unit	LITHO-LOGY	DESCRIPTION	
Late Permian	Khuff Formation	Huqayf Member			Limestone : Cream, dense, burrowed, thickness 6.56'	
Late Carboniferous - Permian	Shajara Formation	Upper Shajara Member	Upper Shajara mudstone		Mudstone : Yellow, thickness 17.7'	
				Upper Shajar Reservoir	SJ13▲	Sandstone : Light brown, cross-bedded, coarse-grained, poorly sorted, porous, friable, thickness 6.5'
					SJ12▲	Sandstone : Yellow, medium-grained, very coarse-grained, poorly, moderately sorted, porous, friable, thickness 13.1'
			SJ11▲			
			Middle Shajara Member	Middle Shajara mudstone		Mudstone : Yellow-green, thickness 11.8'
						Mudstone : Yellow, thickness 1.3'
					Mudstone : Brown, thickness 4.5'	
		Middle Shajara Reservoir		SJ10▲	Sandstone : Light brown, medium-grained, moderately sorted, porous, friable, thickness 3.6'	
				SJ9▲	Sandstone : Yellow, medium-grained, moderately well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 0.9'	
				SJ8▲	Sandstone : Red, coarse-grained, medium-grained, moderately well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 13.4'	
		Lower Shajara Member	Lower Shajara Reservoir	SJ7▲		
				SJ6▲	Sandstone : White with yellow spots, fine-grained, hard, thickness 2.6'	
SJ5▲	Sandstone : Limonite, thickness 1.3'					
SJ4▲	Sandstone : White, coarse-grained, very poorly sorted, thickness 4.5'					
SJ3▲	Sandstone : White-pink, poorly sorted, thickness 1.6'					
SJ2▲	Sandstone : Yellow, medium-grained, well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 3.9'					
		SJ1▲	Sandstone : Red, medium-grained, moderately well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 11.8'			
Early Devonian	Tawil Formation			Sub-Unayzah unconformity. Sandstone : White, fine-grained.		

SJ1 ▲ Samples Collection

Figure 1. Surface type section of the Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation at latitude 26° 52' 17.4" longitude 43° 36' 18".

Figure 2. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ1

Figure 3. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ2

Figure 4. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ3

Figure 5. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ4

As we proceed from sample SJ2 to SJ3 a pronounced reduction in permeability due to compaction was described from 1955 md to 56 md which reflects decrease in Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension from 2.7748 to 2.4379 as quantified in Table 1. Again, an increase in grain size and permeability was proved from sample SJ4 whose seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension was found to be 2.6843 as described in Table 1.

In contrast, the Middle Shajara reservoir which is separated from the Lower Shajara reservoir by an unconformity surface as revealed in Figure 1. It was nominated by four samples (Figure 1), three of which named as SJ7, SJ8, and SJ9 as illuminated in Table1 were chosen for capillary measurements as described in Table 1. Their positive slopes of the first procedure and negative slopes of the second procedure are shown in Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8 and Table 1. Furthermore, their Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimensions and capillary pressure fractal dimensions show similarities as defined in Table 1. Their fractal dimensions are higher than those of samples SJ3 and SJ4 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir due to an increase in their permeability as explained in Table 1.

On the other hand, the Upper Shajara reservoir was separated from the Middle Shajara reservoir by yellow green mudstone as shown in Figure 1. It is defined by three samples so called SJ11, SJ12, SJ13 as explained in Table 1. Their positive slopes of the first procedure and negative slopes of the second procedure are displayed in Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 and Table 1.

Moreover, their seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension are also higher than those of sample SJ3 and SJ4 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir due to an increase in their permeability as simplified in Table 1.

Figure 3. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ7

Figure 4. $\text{Log}(\text{SMM}^{1/4}/\text{SMM}^{1/4}_{\text{max}}) \& \log \text{pc}$ versus $\log \text{Sw}$ for sample SJ8

Figure 5. $\text{Log}(\text{SMM}^{1/4}/\text{SMM}^{1/4}_{\text{max}}) \& \log \text{pc}$ versus $\log \text{Sw}$ for sample SJ9

Figure 6. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ11

Figure 7. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ12

Figure 8. Log (SMM^{1/4}/SMM^{1/4}_{max}) & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ13

Figure 9. Slope of the first procedure versus slope of the second procedure

Figure 10. Seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension versus capillary pressure fractal dimension

Overall a plot of positive slope of the first procedure versus negative slope of the second procedure as described in Figure 12 reveals three permeable zones of varying Petrophysical properties. These reservoir zones were also confirmed by plotting seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension versus capillary pressure fractal dimension as described in Figure 13. Such variation in fractal dimension can account for heterogeneity which is a key parameter in reservoir quality assessment.

4. CONCLUSION

The sandstones of the Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation were divided here into three units based on seismo magnetic moment fractal dimension. The Units from base to top are: Lower Shajara Seismo Magnetic Moment Fractal Dimension Unit, Middle Shajara Seismo Magnetic Moment Fractal Dimension Unit, and Upper Shajara Seismo Magnetic Moment Fractal Dimension Unit. These units were also proved by capillary pressure fractal dimension. The fractal dimension was found to increase with increasing grain size and permeability owing to possibility of having interconnected channels.

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